

A DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS ON SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS STRATEGY OF ONLINE FOOD SERVICE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Food delivery services are now one of the most rapidly growing sectors of digital commerce. The scope of an app between the end-user and the distributor has resulted in the most significant difference between conventional and digital food ordering. The study uses secondary sources of data to analyze the external factors influencing the business model of the online food delivery industry. Porter's Five Force industry analysis model and PESTLE framework is been used in the study with optimistic managerial implications. The analysis shows online food industry has good growth opportunities but to sustain itself in the market, they require to adapt more expansion or competitive strategies to widen their operation capabilities with an increasing customer base. Implications of Online Food Service Industry are been discussed.

Keywords: Online food delivery, Porter's Five Force Model, PESTLE Framework, Competitive Strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the technological development, the commercial service of delivering food items from restaurants to doorsteps of customers is experiencing a sea change as many online channels allow food aggregators to absorb the markets and customers [1]. Restaurants provide electronic ordering via their online sites or mobile platforms serving different restaurants and these restaurants receive orders by text messages, further, the credit point and discount coupon are given to the sales level [2]. Customers are ravenous for such offerings of the online food delivery industry which are discovering to their delight. The majority of the food eaters have shown their proclivity to have food served at the touch of a button instead of waste long stretches swirling ladle in the cup, causing industry growth rates to accelerate.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has the following objectives:

- (1) To identify the various environmental factors affecting the online food industry.
- (2) To analyze the implication of Porter's Five Force Model.
- (2) To analyze the PESTLE Framework analysis.
- (3) To formulate a line of action in areas where there is potential for enhancement of overall operational efficiency.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is descriptive. Current literature was systematically analyzed by the use of Porter's Five Force Model and PESTLE Framework, to comprehend the advances in the Online Food Delivery Industry. To outline and describe various variables that influence the sustainability of food aggregators in the present market, strategies and future demand were explored through the access of secondary data. Data for the study were collected from published sources from sales reports from the official websites of different firms, survey reports, journal research papers, reports issued by different marketing research agencies, and government agencies.

IV. ONLINE FOOD DELIVERY SERVICES IN INDIA

In 2019, the scale of India's online food distribution market reached US\$ 2.9 billion and at present, it has made up to a value of US\$ 4.35 Billion in 2020 which indicates a good flourish in this industry. Ordering food through an online platform refers to the method of using an application on mobiles or accessing a website to order food.

These online platforms allow their customers to build a regular and hassle-free experience to get the food items. These apps or websites offer various options for making the payments such as cash on delivery, debit/credit card, net banking, and mobile wallets, etc. Customers use the online ordering app for convenience, faster delivery, order, reliability, and ease of use, as per the experience of food operators delivering premium online service and the operator's understanding of consumer taste and tastes after estimation [3].

In response to the high accessibility of the internet, facilities have resulted in a rapid increase in smartphone sales. This, in combination with the increasing working population and inflating revenue levels, is driving India's growth in this industry. Currently, many suppliers of online food are available in the market but they are mainly concentrated in cities, with the three largest markets served by Bangalore, Delhi, and Mumbai. Vendors are now also targeting smaller cities because they have strong growth potential. In addition to the growing trend, these vendors offer a home delivery mechanism which provides ease, and inexpensive delivery choice to the customers. During COVID-19, some of the chief delivery aggregators also launched contactless delivery systems, such as McDonald's, Swiggy, Zomato, and Domino's Pizza Inc. [4].

Restaurants spend huge money in designing and furnishing to create a good pleasing ambiance for the customers. Small corporations are constantly outsourcing non-core economic activities, such as food distribution, which was formerly restricted to big corporations. As a result, an increasing number of commercial owners and marketers are becoming aware of the significance of outsourcing food distribution services and are looking into it [5]. Online food delivery system helps to reduce this fixed cost as the food is reached to the customer's doorstep which does not require any investments on fixed cost. Moreover, during busy hours if customers visit restaurants to dine, take more time to finish their meals then the restaurants have to forego a lot of customers. The food distribution sector has phenomenal success in the last four to five years. And this segment's income is rising year after year. As a result, young entrepreneurs are putting their money into the food distribution industry. The below chart shows the revenue in the online food delivery industry.

Chart 1: Exhibits revenue in the Online Food Delivery Industry

As per statistics, in 2021, the exponentially expanding online food distribution market is expected to hit US\$151,526. The online food distribution sector is forecast to expand at a 6.4 percent annual pace (CAGR 2021–2024), resulting in a market volume of US\$182,327 million by 2024 [6].

V. POTENTIAL PLAYERS IN ONLINE FOOD DELIVERY INDUSTRY

Online food ordering has become a popular business concept as people's fascination with digitization grows. The conventional way of delivering food has been transformed by multi-restaurant food delivery apps. Below is the table showing the list of companies in the online food delivery industry with their country of origin and establishment year.

Table-1: Exhibits the list of online food delivery companies

List of Companies	Country of origin	Year of establishment
Zomato	Haryana, India	2008
UberEats	San Francisco, California, U.S.	2014
FoodPanda	Berlin, Germany	2012
Swiggy	Bangalore, India	2014
Grubhub	Chicago, Illinois, U.S.	2004
Deliveroo	London, England, UK	2013
Domino's Pizza	Ypsilanti, Michigan, U.S.	1961
Just Eat	London, England, UK	2001
DoorDash	San Francisco, California, US	2013
Postmates	San Francisco, California, US	2011

VI. PORTER'S FIVE FORCE ANALYSIS OF INDIAN FOOD DELIVERY BUSINESS

A business model is a set of concepts that generates a value proposition by accomplishing a long-term goal. By defining an organization's position in the value chain, the business model describes how it generates profit. The current challenge for organizations is identifying suitable business models that increase customer value and income, as well as systematically analyzing the model [7]. Therefore, Porter's Five Forces model is used in the study to analyze its competitive position. This theory was developed by Harvard's Michael Porter, who used industrial organization economics principles to analyze five interacting factors that are important for a company to become and stay competitive: Competitive rivalry, the threat of new entrants, threat of substitutes, buyer bargaining power, and supplier bargaining power.

(1) Threat of new entrants

Competition increases with the increase of new entrants in the market. If more companies are commenced offering a wide range of products then it may result in a threat to the existing online food suppliers in the market. However, the quality of service, product differences, government policies, brand equity will define the success of the new entrants. Currently, ten online food delivery aggregators are operating successfully in most parts of the country.

The possibility of a new entrant is low because Zomato and Swiggy are the main players in the industry, with a combined market share of 70–80 percent. Swiggy was the industry spearhead in terms of consumer numbers. However, Swiggy is facing stiff competition owing to Zomato's takeover of Uber Eats. In comparison to Swiggy and Zomato, Ola with Food Panda has decelerated on funds [8].

Sustainable Strategy:

The Strategies that may be used to stay competitive to combat the new entrants are as follows:

- (1) Since the threat of new entrants is limited for established players, companies in this industry may pursue an expansion strategy to promote market share by expanding deeper into the Asian economy.
- (2) They can introduce organic food to promote more turnover.
- (3) The strategy must expand its partnerships with as many restaurants and cafes as possible.
- (4) Private brands can manage inorganic development through their cloud kitchens. This concept not only generates inorganic growth but also contributes to the bottom line (profit margins) [9]. Cloud kitchens may be set up in far-flung cities to provide access to healthy food catering zones. This does not necessarily entail a close vicinity venue, nor does it necessitate restaurant repair costs or employee responsibility outside the kitchen apprentices and assistants.
- (5) Food aggregators will also have their Brands, which can be conveniently exhibited on their e-platforms and display posters, owing to this limited operations model. For instance, Zomato has proven to be a broad, user-

friendly portal for getting food across multiple regions, with well-organized content about hotels, nightclubs, cafes, and restaurants, and haute cuisine that is popular among millennials and foodies [10].

(6) Menu choices may be created based on information about regional food tastes.

(7) With fewer opportunities for potential competitors, the primary emphasis of corporate strategies should be on maintaining market share over the viable competitor.

(8) Customer and customer satisfaction are a central component of the strategy. Data on consumer preferences and instances for buying food from outside outlets could be used to create business models [11].

(2) Threat of substitution

The nature of the product determines there is a lot of substitution. Substitution becomes more likely when identical goods are readily available. It is higher due to the widespread availability of related goods. The possibility of substitution can be reduced by having a particular product with distinguishing characteristics. This review allows you to work on product categories and features ahead of time. On these fronts, differentiating goods from the competition will help to mitigate the challenge. There is more rate of risk of substitution as many food delivery apps render similar services on the same network platform. Even though many options are present at the same time, the customers can quickly move from one app to another. If a particular customer surfs for 'Pizza,' online, they can compare both platforms side by side to decide on serving sizes, cost, requirements, and brands. As a result, switching between apps is a critical element of substitution. Substitution risk is inversely related to loyalty towards the brand and negatively impacts its growth. In such a situation, the brand ranking goes hand in hand with cash burns. Higher cash burns lead to higher biggest-grossing, but sustainability remains a major challenge. Therefore, 'Promos' is the main motivation for searching for alternative apps [12]. Food aggregators giving more discount rates are preferred by customers especially for the few who are brand conscious hunt for different apps only to get the promos for their preferred brand. This strategy was adopted by many aggregators but it has further led to more substitution rates. Simultaneously, few popular aggregators do not share their customer details with the restaurateurs and these aggregators establish their relationship with customers therefore it enhances their database of consumer dining habits and also expands its enterprise, which restaurants may see as a contradiction [13].

Sustainable Strategy:

The strategy to sustain the threat of substitution is as follows:

(1) Creating a product or service with distinct characteristics will discourage the customer from switching to other brands. For instance, Swiggy has established a differentiator in the form of a live delivery tracking program based on routing algorithms. Their logistics personnel only handle one order at a time, ensuring that customers get safe and timely orders [14].

(2) Programs to Reward Loyalty should be introduced to the customers who repeatedly use the services. This concept can help to retain the customers at large.

(3) Campaigns to Promote awareness of the services offered should be designed uniquely. Customers must be made aware of the different products and discounts offered or loyalty points.

(4) Relatedness with customers should be given a priority. It could be implemented by designing customer-oriented policies.

(5) To maintain the ordering system's consistency, restaurants can coordinate with consultants to ensure that the interface is available and works well reliably [15].

(3) Bargaining power of the Buyer

This aspect series from moderate to high. Bargaining power increases as the number of alternatives to the consumer soars. Doorstep Service is the most motivating driver for customers, followed by Comfort and Efficiency. When consumers earn some Rewards & Cashbacks, they are most driven, followed by Region [16]. Promotional deals, discounted rates, and a wide range of products provide the customer with many preferences. When it comes to the threat of substitution in online food, the accessibility of comparable items is more important. Similarly, it enhances the customer's bargaining power. Customers are often given more and

more deals by businesses to generate a larger number of customers. However, much of the time, once the deal expires, certain customers leave. This demonstrates the strength of the bargaining position.

Sustainable Strategy:

Higher client bargaining power necessitates planning to have less impact on the upper management and bottom-line. The strategies that may be used to prevent that from happening are as follows.

- (1) Organizations must strive to acquire even more potential customers regularly.
- (2) Customers' bargaining power is reduced as the number of customers continues to grow as such, to address this problem, the product offering ought to be exclusive in terms of quality service and offers.
- (3) Premium subscriptions will aid in the retention of market influence for star players. At an annual cost of INR 1800, Zomato is promoting gold membership to its customers, which includes free shipping and special promotions [17]. This subscription not only provides discounts on orders but also on dining at Zomato's affiliate outlets.
- (4) With lower operating expenses, a food aggregator can deliver cheaper prices. Models such as cloud kitchens may have these benefits [18]. This is an alternative that prevents restaurant upkeep costs and allows food to be delivered at a reduced amount. Providing these cost savings to the consumer will enable you to achieve a competitive advantage over rivals.
- (5) In rural areas, the scope is must be widened. When more technical opportunities open up, the company must take advantage of them by vigorous ads [19].
- (6) The inability of the consumer to review products online poses a danger to the service. Customers are concerned that an open network on the Internet would cause their data to be hacked, resulting in security risks. Online food aggregators should ensure privacy and protection towards payment remitted by online transactions [20].

(4) Bargaining power of supplier:

This characteristic also ranges from moderate to high. Suppliers have the upper hand in most cases when it comes to raw materials. Annual contracts are essential to ensure the uninterrupted supply of expected output [21]. The increase in supplier bargaining power could contribute to higher operating costs. Food galleys, bars, cafes, delicatessens, and fast-food restaurants are examples of vendors in the online food delivery business. When it comes to enrolling providers, standardization is a must. Since India's geography is so diverse, it's critical to consider supply chain issues when evaluating the bargaining power of the supplier. Owing to the smaller volume needs, direct shipments face logistical difficulties in reaching rural areas. Due to multiple handling and long transit times, shipping goods in portion bundles may have an impact on the quality of the product. Spillages and damages also eat into margins, impacting manufacturers' overall compliance. In the regions with low-density logistics, the cost of logistics often increases. When a provider has a national deal with an aggregator, the logistical factor must be taken into account when determining the contract price [22]. It becomes much more essential in the case of low-shelf-life goods, as an uptick in shipping days decreases the product's shelf life. Suppliers also arrange destination prices, making the aggregator's job harder. Paying higher raw material costs in some places for a dish that is priced similarly around the world started to detract from the overall business model. Geographic location, the consumer wants the same flavor of a specific food commodity. While obtaining raw materials is easier in Metropolitan areas, it may be challenging in other cities. Owing to supply chain challenges, suppliers' bargaining power is also considered moderate. With the proliferation of many private logistic networks, logistics and supply platforms can now be considered capable of satisfying customer expectations for speed and timeliness [23]. Besides, large and small restaurants both start whining that they are being propelled to embrace terms and conditions that benefit the aggregators. This entails funding a substantial portion of the discounts solely by the aggregators' service delivery, a significant decrease in meal planning time, and a complete lack of clarity on how in-app reviews work [24].

Sustainable Strategy:

Organizations should use the following techniques to reduce supplier bargaining power:

- (1) Establishing a product range that includes several vendors.

- (2) Designating at least two vendors to prevent reliance and a sense of powerlessness.
- (3) Fixed-price annual arrangements with suppliers can help mitigate and control operating expenses.
- (4) To mitigate mistakes in unusual price hikes and supply, timely analysis of the price is critical.
- (5) Choose vendors which have a professional sales force to help with pricing agreements, distribution issues, and cost-cutting, and new product recommendations.
- (6) Establish inventory standards in a way that allows you to plan ahead of time for supplies from unreliable sources.

(5) Competitive Rivalry:

Global competition has increased in magnitude. In each of the food categories, the rising potential of Indian markets draws many domestic and foreign participants. In India, the e-commerce industry is booming. For the last three years, the online food distribution industry is growing by more than 100 percent [25]. Zomato purchased Uber Eats to gain a leg up on the competition. Zomato made 206 million dollars in revenue in FY19. However, they managed to spend \$500 million on marketing. "We are losing Rs.25 for every delivery," they told reporters [26]. All of this is aimed towards winning market share from Swiggy, the company's primary opponent. Customer satisfaction must be a primary emphasis. If online customers are dissatisfied, they quickly move to competitors because the alternatives are numerous and switching costs are low. As a result, customer engagement is a problem for all companies operating online, necessitating more commitment and solutions to have higher levels of customer loyalty [27].

Sustainable Strategy:

Economic performance is suffering at the hands of the increasing rivalry. It depletes a significant amount of an organization's resources in the fight for market dominance. The below are few strategies for dealing with competitors.

1. Recognizing and merging disparities in customer perception by creating positive awareness about the brand.
2. Online food delivery service providers must make sure that the food delivers in a reasonable amount of time, and the lead time can be as minimal as possible to prevent customers from using alternative delivery methods [28].
3. Creating a varied offering portion to provide distinction and gain a competitive advantage through differentiation strategy. In comparison to others, Zomato is proactive in its promotions as it incorporates guerrilla marketing [29].
4. The top priority should be innovation. Shoppers are particularly attracted to innovation.
5. Enhancing the quality of service provided to customers by offering many promos, discounts, etc.

VII. PESTLE ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK

Companies use PESTLE analysis to monitor the world in which they work or to schedule the introduction of a new project/product/service, etc. The system offers the view of an entire ecosystem from a range of viewpoints that one may want to review and keep track of when considering a particular concept or strategy. Each of the factors varies depending on the sector, but the PESTLE analysis is needed for any strategy a business wishes to develop because it is a much more detailed version of the SWOT analysis [30]. It is used for a qualitative report on a company's or industry's external environmental analysis. Such models/techniques make it simple and comprehensive to define various factors/issues that affect a person's individual or an organization's system, as well as offer areas of improvement [31].

(1) Political

Every food industry experiences a wide regulatory structure from the government around the world. This includes the hygiene of industrial scullery and kitchens, the criteria for storage and conveying products, and also the specifications for staff. This makes the food industry, without a doubt, one of the most closely controlled industries of all. On the positive side, this means that customers are not subjected to low-quality nutrition, but the regulatory complexities are certainly eliminated from the food sector margins. In addition to the regulations, online food aggregators also need to follow certain terms and conditions in respect to a background check of the workforce, proper training in delivering the food within the prescribed limits.

(2) Economic

According to the Boston Consulting Company, India's food sector was worth about 23 trillion rupees in 2015, and it is projected to cross 42 lakh crores by 2020 [32]. This is consequential due to an increase in population. Amidst the growing population, the majority of them belong to the young crowd which demands more fast food in their appetite leading to the growth of this industry. The young generation is mostly placed in information technology, tourism, finance sector, and hospitality which has increased their standard of living and made them wealthier. Many places witness some changes in the social pattern which is again responsible for the boom in this industry. This has a positive impact on the growth of restaurateurs, distributors of food, and even the workforce of these online food delivery industries.

In addition to population growth and employment opportunities, the disposable income of citizens is growing rapidly resulting in a better standard of living. Moreover, the laborers are earning more money, and overall, in all sectors, the cost of recruiting employees is growing which has triggered not only increasing demand for jobs but also higher and higher government minimum wage standards. The result of growing labor costs is clear, as in many other businesses: less margin for the owner of the company, and therefore less benefit. During COVID-19 many food distributors were running under loss due to non-operations of the restaurant businesses. As the market conditions improved, with the upliftment of lockdown, slowly restaurants were operating with contactless delivery as per government regulations which boosted some opportunities for food aggregators. Post-COVID - 19 many restaurants got listed as member participants to offer food online as demands from more people to dine in with family in caution to safety issues. This has led to a boom in the online food industry. In addition to this, the companies in these industries would need to raise additional money to expand globally. Since the financial system is different, it takes time to set up bank accounts and conduct transactions [33].

(3) Social

With the changes in lifestyle and diet, people are aware that there exists a relationship between diet and our bodies. There is a direct relationship between the food we consume and one's well-being. As a result, many people are searching for healthy ways to source their bodies. The failure to view or handle the product physically, as well as concerns regarding the mechanisms of terms and conditions of food supply and thereof, refunds, and the distribution of credit card number sharing over the Internet, are all seen as shortcomings [34]. This does not inherently have a positive or negative impact on the food industry, but it ensures that to remain competitive, food industry players in the market will have to change. Quick food firms, for instance, would probably have to switch away from conventional, high-calorie fried foods to healthier alternatives such as salads. Moreover, in connection to a higher standard of living, some lifestyle changes have been noticed especially in urban India with dual family earners who find difficulty on managing quality time for spending with family members leading to a drastic shift of food habits giving a rising demand for quick access to food items at reasonable prices, especially cooked food products. Currently, in many cities, more women have become earning supporters. Therefore, much of the women's productive hour is spent on traveling and at jobs. As a result, working females have less time to prepare proper food at home. Thus, these women usually spent a substantial portion of their discretionary income to have food ordered from out to dine in with family members. Online food delivery services can reduce home cooking, which may have an impact on customers' balanced diet quality. As a consequence, it's difficult to maintain customers [35].

(4) Technology

As a result of rising consumer access internet and smartphones, many players are penetrating the Indian food market sector. The customer has a hassle-free experience when the whole process is made easy. Paper wasting can be eliminated while dining at the restaurant because it is done on a tablet and no paperwork is needed [36]. The performance of any business, as a general rule, lies in certain critical variables. The choice of advanced technology and the company's future vision are most critical to conduct a comprehensive market analysis. Advanced technology interface has led to advancing market share, increase in potential profits, and structuring competitive advantage. In this digital era, Information and Communication Technology has been proven to be a critical tool to gain and sustain a competitive advantage over other troupes in the industry. Indian customers

find it very easy and convenient to operate digital applications for browsing online shopping sites, as such they expect the same experience with online food ordering[37]. Food providers need to analyze the issues on operations of digital apps and focus on solving the difficulties faced by online users. They need to structure a platform that offers a 'user appealing experience' that eventually improves the level of satisfaction of the customer. Food aggregators must use low-cost technology and find new methods and designs to create sites that most appealing to the customers to increase their desire to order food online. Currently, the demand is to create value for the customers. For instance, to produce more sales, Zomato is one of India's foremost food aggregators which began offering a variety of goods and services, besides this, they too render services such as Zomato Foundation, Zomato Book, and Zomato White which has made the revenue model more sustainable, along with business consulting services.

(5) Legal

The food industry faces high expectations for safety problems. In each country, in particular, there are many rules about how food should be transported, processed, and prepared, including guidelines on what temperatures different types of food should reach, how to clean them, and so on. While this is still primarily a political issue, if any of these laws are ever broken, it becomes a legal matter. As such, to avoid expensive litigation, those in the food industry need to be exceedingly alert to ensure that they remain within the limits of these regulations. Therefore, food aggregators must consider fulfilling all the conditions in respect to delivering quality food and list only those restaurants that strictly adhere to government rules in food preparation. The Internet's erratic existence, which is out of the control of its owners and users, poses a threat to the environment. It raises a financial risk as well as privacy concerns [38]. Many online sites design food items exaggerating their appearance and quality, if false information and description of the food is given to mislead any customer, will lead to litigation charges.

(6) Environmental

There is a lot of social awareness regarding the health effects of any food we consume and how it affects the environment. Some of the foodstuffs like red meat processing use more water and it releases a large carbon footprint. Moreover, this meat processing farm setup requires a huge manufacturing plant. The effect of this is that more and more people are transitioning to diets based on plants, and policymakers are increasingly taking an interest. Again, for food producers, this is not inherently negative, but they will have to consider the long-term effect of this change. Besides, packed foodstuff is delivered by use of plastic waste. Therefore, online food aggregators must consider the demands of customers and insist the restaurant member cook healthy food and go for eco-friendly packaging.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In India, one of the most common new trends in online food delivery. The average Indian's modern social lifestyle pattern is substantial enough to stimulate the development of food-on-the-go and swift online delivery platforms. The ever-increasing population especially in congested metro cities, longer travel times, ready-to-eat, and less expensive alternative of getting food delivered to one's door are all driving factors for the growth of this online food industry. Porter's Five Force analysis and PESTLE analysis were used in the study to find different strategies for sustainability. The study reflects that the online food delivery industry must introduce new features by upgrading their apps and offer more promos or discounts to retain the existing customers and also for increasing their customer base. However, the boom in this industry has increased the level of work openings for youngsters in the sector and has raised the quality of living. India's GDP will rise as a result of emerging trends in the online foodservice industry.

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